

LINCS Dataset Intake Questionnaire

Version 2.2 | Last updated 2025 05 06

A copy of this questionnaire is created for each LINCS project. Data stewards are welcome to make their own copy to fill in and share with the LINCS team, or they can ask the LINCS team to create a copy for them.

This questionnaire does not need to be completed all at once. Please feel free to return to it as you gather more information.

A. DATASET INFORMATION

Dataset name	
Dataset long name	
Dataset short name	
Dataset identifier	

Data steward team				
Last name	First name	Email address	Role (e.g., lead, research assistant)	ORCID
[Add rows as needed]				

B. RESEARCH

B.1 Research Information

Dataset and project descriptions
[Optional] Provide a short description of your research project (100–120 words; 600–720 characters). <i>This is a description of the origins of your project and the questions, topics, and approaches behind it.</i>

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[Optional] Provide a short description of your dataset (100–120 words; 600–720 characters). *This is a description of the materials that you are using to create your dataset and the main categories that your dataset will include.*

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[Optional] Provide a 1–2 sentence description of your dataset (10–20 words).

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LINCS will ask you to provide keywords in a linked data format for your dataset ahead of publication. You can provide these now using the [LINCS keywords form](#), or you can provide some more general keywords here to start, and we can generate linked data keywords later.

I have used the [LINCS keywords form](#)

I am providing preliminary keywords here

Does your dataset have any Canadian content? If yes, please provide more information.

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Does your dataset have any Indigenous content? If yes, please provide more information.

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What time period is covered by the dataset?

What languages are used in the dataset?

What languages are used in metadata?

B.2 Ethics Review

Did your project require an ethics review? If yes, please provide more information, including the status of your ethics application and/or a link to your ethics application or certificate.

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B.3 Research Questions

What are you trying to find out from your research, in general (not just from linked open data)? What are your research questions?
What kinds of questions might you ask of it once it is linked? Are these questions you are unable to answer using the data in its current form? If you know what SPARQL queries are, what kinds of queries might you make?
Who is the audience for your data? What kinds of users is it composed of (general interest, specialists, etc.)? How big is this audience?

B.4 Social Media

Project website	
Project social media	

B.5 Related Projects

Do you know of any similar datasets or projects, within or beyond LINCS? If yes, please provide more information and/or provide links to where we can find out more.
Are there any existing projects that are models for what you are doing? If yes, please provide more information and/or provide links to where we can find out more.
Are there any datasets or projects you would like to connect with?

C. TECHNICAL

C.1 Dataset

Data type	
Data types (e.g., structured, semi-structured, TEI, natural language)	
File types (e.g., CSV, XML)	
Size (e.g., MB, number of documents)	
Content (e.g., text-based, multimedia)	

Data acquisition and formatting
Where did your data come from? Did you create it? Did you scrape it from somewhere?
Have you finished collecting your data? Do you intend to collect more?
Do you intend to continue making formatting or content changes to your data? Are you ready to start working towards transforming your data into linked open data
How many entities are represented in your data (e.g., people, places)?
How many types of relationships are represented in your data (e.g., A is the author of B book, C is the child of D)?

Do you have any of the following? If yes, please provide details.	
Ontologies	
Vocabularies	
Authorities	
Schemas or defined tagsets	

URIs	
DOIs	

Are you using [TEI](#)? If so, which tags matter most to you? Which tags do you want to see mobilized?

What is unique or interesting about your dataset? Is there something we should showcase about it?

Granularity and specificity

What level of granularity (detail/specificity) is in your dataset? How detailed are the connections between things and other things, and/or details about those things (between entities and properties)? Perhaps think about it as are you talking about a “place” at the level of a planet, continent, country, city, street, house, room, floorspace taken up by chairs around a table? Evidence in a book at the level of the book, edition, chapter, page, line, location of word within line?

How do you conceptualize and represent different types and levels of (un)certainty in your dataset? What signifiers (like words such as “maybe”, or the addition of a “?” in connection to an entry) do you use, and what about (un)certainty are you representing through their application?

What does “provenance” mean to you in the context of this dataset, and what data do you have that represents that? What do you consider to be important to keep track of, and at what level of granularity (e.g., provenance for dataset as a whole versus each datum)?

C.2 Access

Source Data Access	
Is your data open or licensed (e.g., CC-BY)?	
Is your data behind a login or paywall?	
Are there any limitations to access the data?	

Ownership	
Who owns the data?	
If someone else owns the data, who is the owner?	
If someone else owns the data, do you have permission to use it? Please provide details.	
Who created the dataset?	
Once it is prepared as linked data, who will own the linked data?	

Source Data Storage	
Who currently has the data?	
Where is it located?	
How do we get it?	
Is your data archived in a long-term preservation system? If so, how?	[Please provide a link to your long-term preservation plan, if available]
Does your data have DOIs ?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Data Publication and Access	
LINCS publishes linked open data. If your data cannot be published as open data using a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license, you will need to arrange an exemption before proceeding.	
Would you like to discuss an exemption?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
LINCS uses a public GitLab repository to manage the data transformation process. Data stored in this GitLab repository is publicly available although not typically found via web searches. Can LINCS use a public GitLab repository:	
To store your pre-transformation data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

To store your data throughout the transformation process?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
To store your transformed data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If you select no for any of the above, the data from the relevant stage (pre-transformation, in transformation, and/or transformed) will be stored in either (a) a private Google Drive folder, or (b) a GitLab repository accessible only by the LINCS core team and your data steward team. Note that this workflow is not optimal and may require additional time and resources.	<input type="checkbox"/> I understand
<p>Prior to publication, your transformed data is available for you to review and test in the review environments of LINCS tools, such as ResearchSpace and the Context Explorer. The LINCS review environment is a shared space, which means that other teams with access to the environment at the same time will also be able to see (but not edit) your data.</p> <p>Once your data is in the LINCS review environment, the names of the entities described in your dataset (and some additional information, but not their full descriptions) will also be viewable by select LINCS users via tools such as OpenRefine and NERVE. Users will be informed that they are accessing draft data.</p>	
Check here to confirm that you understand that your review data will be subject to limited access by other teams.	<input type="checkbox"/> I understand

C.3 Processing

What does your data need in order to be mobilized as linked open data? Check all that apply.	
Named entity recognition or entity extraction	<input type="checkbox"/>
Disambiguation and entity matching	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mapping and/or ontology crosswalking	<input type="checkbox"/>

Who will review and vet your data? Check all that apply.		
	Source data	Transformed data
Project lead and/or co-leads	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Members of my team	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Research assistants	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I would like help from the LINCS team with reviewing and vetting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

How familiar are you with linked open data? Tell us about your knowledge and/or experience.

Are you and/or your team comfortable with the following types of interfaces? Check all that apply.

	Extremely comfortable	Somewhat comfortable	Uncomfortable	I don't know what this is
GUIs (web-based tools or installed programs such as Open Refine, CWRC-Writer)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Command line	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Programming tools and notebooks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forming SQL or SPARQL queries	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

How involved do you want to be in technical processing?

How involved do you want your students, research assistants, or other team members to be in the technical processing? What are the areas of expertise of these team members (e.g., subject-matter knowledge, technical knowledge)?

If you plan to process your data independently, do you anticipate needing resources such as compute cycles or storage?

Are there any dependencies on which you're waiting (within or beyond LINCS) in order to proceed? If so, what are they?

D. ADMINISTRATIVE

D.1 Project Participants

Do you have (or have plans to) expand your team?				
	Yes, I have already	I have plans to add	No, I do not plan to add	To be determined
Research assistants	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Technical support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other team members	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

What kind of training and consultation do you anticipate wanting from LINCS? Check all that apply.	
Introduction to linked open data	<input type="checkbox"/>
Understanding ontologies	<input type="checkbox"/>
Choosing linked open data authorities and vocabularies	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cleaning and reconciling data	<input type="checkbox"/>
Introduction to LINCS tools (e.g., LEAF-Writer , ResearchSpace)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Is there any other training or consultation you would like LINCS to provide? If yes, please describe it here.

D.2 Timelines

What is the current status of your project (e.g., awaiting funding, in progress)?

What is your project timeline? Do you have a deadline? Do you have an estimate for when you would be ready to proceed with LINCS?
Do you have any funding-related deadlines or limitations? If yes, please describe.
When do you think you might be ready to start working with LINCS to create linked open data?
Are there any dependencies (within or beyond LINCS) that you need to meet in order to proceed? If yes, please describe.

How much time (week/month/term) do you have for the project?	
Project lead or co-leads	
Students	
Other team members	
Are there times you will or will not be able to work?	

E. FUNDING

E.1 Applications

Are you applying for or have you secured funding to support your work with LINCS?	
I am applying for funding	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have secured funding	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not need funding to support this work	<input type="checkbox"/>
To be determined	<input type="checkbox"/>

E.2 Additional Funding Information

If you are applying for or have secured funding, please provide details about the grant and any associated deadlines (internal and external).

Does your institution require an agreement (e.g., a subaward agreement, memorandum of understanding, inter-institutional agreement, or statement of work) to establish a funding relationship?

Yes

No

I don't know

Please provide contact details for the individual at your institution who will be handling funding (e.g., research office).

Name

Position

Email address

F. CONCLUDING QUESTIONS

Please provide us with links to where we can download a copy of your data or email the data to lincs@uoguelph.ca.

Data sample

Full data dump

Where did you hear about LINCS?

Would you like to be added to our list of prospective user testers?

Yes

No